

Trends in Experimental Animal Use in Spain and Europe: A Multi-Year Statistical Analysis

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Abstract: This study provides a comprehensive analysis of experimental animal use in Spain (2009–2023) and the European Union (2015–2022), across research fields, disease models, and species. Between 2009 and 2013, fundamental biology dominated animal use in Spain, with notable declines after 2009. Disease-related studies showed high usage in other human diseases and cancer, while cardiovascular models increased. From 2014 to 2023, basic research remained prominent but was overtaken by translational and applied research after 2020, reflecting evolving research priorities. Human cancer remained the most studied disease model, though its use declined after 2017. Mice were consistently the most used species in both Spain and the EU, reaffirming their central role in biomedical research. Fish species, including zebrafish and sea bass, gained importance, particularly in developmental studies. COVID-19 did not significantly alter total animal use patterns, though minor, statistically non-significant fluctuations occurred. The results highlight long-term trends, shifts in species preferences, and the need for continued efforts in reducing and refining animal use in scientific research.

Keywords: experimental animal use; fundamental biology; cancer; cardiovascular models; COVID 19

1. Introduction

The use of animals in scientific research has a long and complex history, deeply intertwined with humanity's quest for knowledge in medicine and biology. From ancient civilizations to modern laboratories, animal experimentation played a crucial role in advancing medical and scientific discoveries. Early scholars such as Aristotle (384–322 BCE) and Galen (129–216 CE) conducted dissections on animals to understand anatomy and physiology, shaping medical thought for centuries [1]. During the Renaissance, figures like Andreas Vesalius and William Harvey revolutionized the study of human and animal biology through meticulous dissections and experimentation [2,3]. By the 19th and 20th centuries, animal models became essential for biomedical breakthroughs, leading to the development of vaccines, surgical techniques, and drug testing [3].

However, alongside these advancements, ethical concerns surrounding animal welfare grew, especially in response to the increasing scale of animal use in research. This led to the development of formal ethical guidelines, culminating in the 3Rs principle (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) proposed by Russell and Burch in 1959 [4].

While the 3Rs have influenced research policies worldwide, the scale and regulation of animal experimentation vary significantly between regions. In the European Union (EU), Directive 2010/63/EU has established one of the world's most comprehensive regulatory frameworks, emphasizing ethical oversight, reduction strategies, and alternative methods. In contrast, other regions, including the United States, China, and Japan, have distinct regulatory approaches that, while incorporating ethical principles, may differ in their implementation of the 3Rs. For example, while the EU has made significant progress in reducing animal use in certain research fields, some countries outside Europe continue

to see an increase in animal testing, particularly in pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries where alternative methods are still under development [5].

Despite these regulatory differences, fundamental biology, medical research, and safety evaluations remain the dominant fields of animal experimentation globally. However, the extent to which these fields adopted reduction strategies remains uncertain. This study aims to analyze the trends in experimental animals used across different research fields and disease models in Spain and Europe over recent years.

In addition to long-term trends, recent global events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have raised questions about how external crises influence research practices. The pandemic disrupted scientific workflows, altering funding priorities, laboratory access, and research focus, particularly in biomedical fields. Given these disruptions, we sought to examine whether COVID-19 significantly impacted animal use patterns in Spain and across Europe.

By incorporating this analysis, this study provides a comprehensive perspective on experimental animal use, capturing both possible long-term trends and short-term disruptions. This approach helps assess whether research practices, particularly in disease modeling and biomedical studies, align with the 3Rs principle and how external factors may shape the future of animal experimentation in Europe.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Data compilation

All data compilation, processing, and statistical analysis were conducted between January and March 2025. This study involved a comprehensive evaluation of the number and purpose of animals used in research in Spain from 2009 to 2023. Data were obtained from official reports published by the “Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación” (MAPA) [Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, and Food], available at: (https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/ganaderia/temas/produccion-y-mercados-ganaderos/bien-estanimal/en-la-investigacion/Informes_y_publicaciones.aspx).

Data from Spain were divided into two periods based on reporting methodology. For the years 2009–2013, statistics referred to the number of animals used in experiments, while data from 2014–2023 were reported in terms of animal uses. For 2009–2013, datasets were extracted and organized into Excel spreadsheets based on information from the sections: “Número de animales utilizados en experimentos para fines concretos” (Number of animals used in experiments for specific purposes) and “Número de animales utilizados en experimentos para estudios sobre enfermedades humanas y animales” (Number of animals used in experiments for studies on human and animal diseases).

For the period 2014–2023, the datasets were structured according to the following categories: “Número de usos de cada especie o grupo de especies animales utilizadas” (Number of uses of each animal species or group of species), “Número de usos de animales según la finalidad de los usos” (Number of animal uses by purpose), and “Número de usos de animales según la finalidad de los usos – Investigación traslacional y aplicada” (Number of animal uses by purpose – Translational and applied research).

At the European level, data from 2015 to 2022 were retrieved from the ALURES (Animal Use Reporting – EU Statistics) database, specifically Section 1: Numbers of Animals Used for Research, Testing, Routine Production, and Education and Training Purposes in the EU. Each reporting year was accessed individually, and the data were transposed into Excel files for further analysis. Although the original database was available at https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/envdataportal/content/alures/section1_number-of-animals.html.

2.2. Statistical analysis

All analysis were performed in R (version 4.3.2). Data normality was evaluated using histograms and q-q plots. Since the data did not follow a normal distribution, non-parametric tests were applied.

For multi-group comparisons across years, the Friedman test was used, followed by Dunn's post-hoc test for pairwise comparisons where significant differences were found. To assess differences between the pre-COVID (≤ 2019) and post-COVID (> 2019) periods, the Wilcoxon rank-sum test was applied. Multiple comparisons were adjusted using both Bonferroni and Benjamini-Hochberg (FDR) corrections.

3. Results

3.1. Distribution of animals across research fields in Spain (2009–2013)

The analysis of animals across different research fields revealed notable variations between 2009 and 2013. Fundamental biology studies accounted for the highest number of animals used, with a mean of $650,850.6 \pm 239,002.6$. The large range (min = 468,269, max = 949,032) indicates periods of heightened activity in this field. Notably, after a peak in 2009, the number of animals used in fundamental biology declined sharply in 2011 and remained lower in subsequent years (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of animals across research fields in Spain (2009–2013).

Other research fields demonstrated moderate number. Research and development of medical, dental, and veterinary products and instruments exhibited a relatively high and stable mean of $166,035.8 \pm 5,754.1$, highlighting its consistent importance in preclinical studies. Safety evaluations had a mean of $92,225.6 \pm 27,417.3$, with a wide range (min = 69,255, max = 127,713), peaking in 2010 before experiencing a decline. Moreover, production and quality control of veterinary products and instruments showed greater variability ($49,271.8 \pm 15,816.0$), with a notable increase in 2013.

No statistically significant differences were found in the total number of animals used between 2009 and 2013 (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 1.7$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.7907$). However, when comparing different research fields, a significant difference was observed (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 32$, $df = 7$, $p = 4.062 \times 10^{-5}$), suggesting that the number of animals varied across research fields. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction identified significant differences between education training vs. fundamental biology. ($p_{\text{adj}} = 6.17 \times 10^{-5}$), education training vs. medical research. ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0014$), education training vs. safety evaluations ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0223$), fundamental biology vs. medical production ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0477$), and fundamental biology vs. others ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0053$).

No other pairwise comparisons reached statistical significance after Bonferroni correction ($p_{\text{adj}} > 0.05$). Full details, including descriptive statistics, normality assessments (histograms and q-q plots), and the complete results of Dunn's post-hoc pairwise comparisons, are provided in Supplementary Materials.

3.2. Distribution of animals across disease categories in Spain (2009–2013)

The analysis of animals used across different disease models revealed notable variations between 2009 and 2013. Other human diseases accounted for the highest number of animals used, with a mean of $190,614 \pm 8,135.6$. The peak was observed in 2009 with 202,485 animals, while the lowest count occurred in 2013 with 182,196 animals. Moreover, human cancer models also exhibited substantial number of animal used ($149,847.8 \pm 16,653.5$), peaking in 2012, with 173,202 animals, before declining in 2013 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of animals across disease models in Spain (2009–2013).

The number of animals in human cardiovascular diseases showed an increasing trend, reaching a maximum in 2013 (53,358 animals), while nervous and mental disorders remained relatively stable ($115,757.4 \pm 5,968.7$). Specific studies of animal diseases exhibited the lowest mean ($38,926.6 \pm 5,785.2$), though an increase was observed after 2011.

No statistically significant differences were found in the total number of animals used for disease-related research between 2009 and 2013 (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 0.48$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.9754$). However, when comparing different disease categories, significant differences were observed (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 19.36$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.0006677$), suggesting that certain disease areas consistently used different numbers of animals across years.

Post hoc analysis using Dunn's test identified specific significant differences between disease categories after Bonferroni correction. The number of animals used for animal diseases studies differed significantly from human cancer ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.030$) and other human diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.00054$). Additionally, significant differences were observed between human cardiovascular diseases and other human diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0050$). Full details are provided in Supplementary Materials.

3.3. Animal use across research fields in Spain (2014–2023)

The analysis of animal uses across different research fields between 2014 and 2023 revealed that basic research accounted for the highest average number of animal uses, with a mean of $374,343.4 \pm 54,161.8$. However, a notable declining trend was observed over the period, starting from 448,149 animal uses in 2014 and decreasing to 315,671 in 2023, with a particularly sharp drop in 2017 (329,493) and continued reductions in subsequent years. Translational and applied research, while having a slightly lower mean ($349,042.7 \pm 249,908.8$), exhibited much greater variability, with a notable rise in animal use from 2014 to 2017. This upward trend was followed by a sharp decline in 2018. However, after 2018, the number of animal uses began to increase again, reaching its highest peak in 2021, with a total of 792,992 uses (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Number of animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023).

No statistically significant differences were found in the total number of animal uses across research fields between 2014 and 2023 (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 8.13$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.5211$). However, when analyzing differences across specific research fields, significant variation was detected (Friedman test, $\chi^2 = 64.07$, $df = 7$, $p = 2.316 \times 10^{-11}$), suggesting that certain research fields exhibited distinct patterns of animal use over time.

Post hoc analysis using Dunn's test identified specific statistically significant differences between fields after Bonferroni correction. Notably, basic research differed significantly from forensic investigations ($p_{\text{adj}} = 3.10 \times 10^{-9}$), higher education or training for the acquisition, maintenance, or improvement of professional skills ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0063$), protection of the natural environment in the interest of human or animal health or wellbeing ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0010$), and species preservation ($p_{\text{adj}} = 1.33 \times 10^{-6}$).

Similarly, forensic investigations showed significant differences compared to maintenance of colonies of genetically altered animals not used in other procedures ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0047$), regulatory use and routine production ($p_{\text{adj}} = 2.19 \times 10^{-5}$), and translational and applied research ($p_{\text{adj}} = 2.82 \times 10^{-7}$).

Protection of the natural environment in the interest of human or animal health or wellbeing also showed significant differences compared to translational and applied research ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.018$). Regulatory use and routine production showed significant differences compared to species preservation ($p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0022$). Finally, species preservation showed significant differences compared to translational and applied research ($p_{\text{adj}} = 6.06 \times 10^{-5}$). Full details are provided in Supplementary Materials.

3.4. Animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023)

The analysis of animal uses across different disease models between 2014 and 2023 revealed notable variations. Human cancer accounted for the highest number of animal uses, with a mean of $55,872.3 \pm 33,872.9$. The highest usage was recorded in 2017, with 116,595 uses, followed by a sharp decrease in subsequent years. Animal diseases also represented a significant portion of animal uses, with a mean of $43,914.4 \pm 17,145.2$ (min = 18, max = 60,105). Usage remained relatively stable over the years, with a peak in 2019 (60,105 uses) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Number of animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023).

Animal welfare exhibited the highest variability ($37,029.4 \pm 66,954.5$), characterized by relatively low and fluctuating values in the early years, followed by a sharp peak in 2022 with 222,793 animal uses.

Other disease categories showed moderate to lower usage. Human nervous and mental diseases ($21,840.2 \pm 9,270.5$) and human endocrine and metabolic diseases ($15,269.6 \pm 9,060.8$) ranked next in overall animal uses, reflecting their importance in biomedical research. Meanwhile, human respiratory diseases ($2,638.7 \pm 1325.4$) and human musculoskeletal diseases ($2,732.6 \pm 1102.7$) had lower mean values.

The lowest usage was recorded from other human diseases (869.6 ± 1198.5) and plant diseases (8.4 ± 6.7), highlighting the uneven distribution of animal uses across research fields.

The Friedman test was applied to assess whether the total number of animal uses in disease research in Spain fluctuated significantly over time (2014–2023). The results indicated a significant difference across years ($\chi^2 = 43.428$, $df = 9$, $p = 1.799e-06$), confirming that total number of animal uses varied throughout this period. Dunn's test indicated statistically significant differences between 2014 and all subsequent years (2015–2023).

In contrast, a second Friedman test was conducted to evaluate whether the number of animal uses differed significantly among disease model categories over the 2014–2023 period. The results indicated a highly significant overall difference ($\chi^2 = 124.45$, $df = 16$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). Post-hoc analysis using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction identified 20 significant pairwise differences. The most significant differences were observed between animal diseases and plant diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 2.66 \times 10^{-7}$), and between human cancer and plant diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 1.79 \times 10^{-7}$), both showing extremely low adjusted p-values. Other notable comparisons included animal diseases versus other human diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 2.92 \times 10^{-5}$), human cancer versus other human diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 2.08 \times 10^{-5}$), and human nervous and mental diseases versus plant diseases ($p_{\text{adj}} = 1.45 \times 10^{-5}$). In addition, significant differences were found between several human disease categories and either plant diseases or other human diseases. A complete summary of descriptive statistics, normality tests, and the full post-hoc results, including non-significant comparison, is provided in Supplementary Materials.

3.5 Distribution of animals species across research fields in Spain (2009–2013)

Mice were consistently the most frequently used species in research, particularly in fundamental biology studies. Their use in this area rose from 307,082 animals in 2009 to a peak of 395,921 in 2012, followed by a slight decline to 382,849 in 2013 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Heatmap of species used across research fields in Spain (2009–2013).

Fish also played a prominent role in research, particularly in fundamental biology studies, where they reported the highest numbers of animals used in some years. Notably, their use peaked in 2009 (580,713) and remained high in 2010 (465,554), before declining steadily from 2011 to 2013.

3.6 Distribution of animals species across disease models in Spain (2009–2013)

Between 2009 and 2013, animal models played a crucial role in advancing research across a wide range of human diseases in Spain. Mice emerged as the most frequently used species, consistently recording the highest numbers each year, especially in cancer research. Their dominance was particularly evident in human cancer studies, where they were the primary model organism, peaking at 167,573 animals in 2012. Mice were also integral to research on cardiovascular diseases, nervous and mental disorders, and other human diseases, solidifying their importance as a versatile model in biomedical research (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Heatmap of species used across disease models in Spain (2009–2013).

Rats also played a significant role in research. In 2009, rats were notably used in the study of other human diseases, with a peak of 50,113 animals in this category. Over the years, rat usage remained prominent, particularly in neurological and behavioral studies. However, their use gradually decreased by 2013, reflecting shifting trends in animal model preferences and research focus.

3.7 Distribution of animal species in Spain (2014–2023)

Between 2014 and 2023, 42 animal species were used for experimental purposes in Spain. Among them, mice stood out as the most frequently used species throughout the entire period, reaching a peak of 539,974 uses in 2016. Although the number of uses fluctuated in the following years (523,467 in 2017, 518,282 in 2018, and a decline to 404,438 in 2020) mice continued to be indispensable, underscoring their essential role in research.

In addition, several other species also contributed to experimental research. Rats, poultry, zebrafish, and other fish were used at moderate levels, with their usage numbers varying each year. These species, while not reaching the same levels as mice, played crucial roles in specific areas of research.

In addition to traditional laboratory animals, certain aquatic species gained prominence in specific years. Sea bass (species of the family Serranidae or Moronidae) for instance, showed exceptionally high values in 2021 (526,820 uses) and 2023 (337,536 uses). (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Heatmap of annual animal uses by species in Spain (2014–2023).

3.8 Distribution of animal species at european level (2014–2023)

At the european level, 41 animal species were reported for research purposes between 2015 and 2022. Mice were consistently the most used species, peaking at 5,989,413 in 2016, followed by a decline to 3,879,691 in 2020 and a partial recovery in subsequent years. Rats showed a similar trend, dropping from 1,201,189 in 2015 to 625,777 in 2022. Fish species, notably zebrafish, sea bass, and salmonids, also played a significant role. Zebrafish fluctuated between 513,011 in 2016 and 277,328 in 2020. Other fish peaked at 2.3 million in 2018 and remained high in later years. Sea bass reached 646,076 in 2021, and salmon, trout, charrs and graylings surpassed 1.9 million in 2021 (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Heatmap of annual animal used by species in the EU (2015–2022).

3.9 Experimental animal use before and after COVID-19 in Spain: trends and variability

The total number of animals used pre- and post-COVID-19 did not show statistically significant differences across species when applying multiple comparison corrections. The Wilcoxon test results suggested potential differences in species like cats ($p = 0.00952$), rabbits ($p = 0.01900$), and sheep ($p = 0.03810$), but these findings were not significant after Bonferroni and Benjamini-Hochberg corrections ($p_{\text{adj}} > 0.05$ in all cases). These results indicate that while fluctuations in specific species were observed, they may be attributed to natural variability rather than systematic changes due to the pandemic. Further statistical comparisons and detailed results are provided in Supplementary Materials.

3.10 Experimental animal use before and after COVID-19 in Europe: trends and variability

At the European level, similar patterns of variation in species usage were observed. The Wilcoxon test initially indicated significant differences for several species, including cynomolgus monkeys, dogs, guinea pigs, mice, rats, and sheep ($p = 0.0357$ for each). However, after applying Bonferroni correction, none of these differences remained statistically significant ($p_{\text{adj}} > 0.05$). Likewise, the Benjamini-Hochberg adjustment resulted in adjusted p -values above the 0.05 threshold for all species, suggesting that no significant changes in animal use occurred at the European level.

4. Discussion

Understanding trends in animal research is crucial for evaluating scientific priorities, ethical considerations, and regulatory compliance. However, a major challenge in assessing long-term patterns lies in the lack of homogenization across research entities, regulatory frameworks, and data reporting methods. Differences in criteria used to categorize animal models, variations in how data are collected and shared, and changes in transparency policies over time complicate direct comparisons between studies and countries. This disparity not only hinders efforts to establish clear trends in animal use but also limits the effectiveness of collaborative strategies aimed at refining and reducing animal experimentation.

One of the main obstacles is the variation in reporting standards across different institutions and nations. The absence of standardized methodologies for classifying research fields, species usage, and experimental purposes makes it difficult to draw uniform conclusions from available data. For instance, while some regions emphasize the detailed classification of species and experimental objectives, others provide aggregated data, reducing granularity and impeding precise trend analysis. Moreover, regulatory updates and shifts in public policies over the years have altered how data are reported, further complicating historical comparisons.

The implementation of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) has been another major factor influencing animal research trends. While efforts to replace animal models with alternative methodologies have gained momentum, their adoption remains uneven across disciplines. Certain fields, such as toxicology and pharmaceutical development, have successfully integrated computational models and organ-on-a-chip technologies, whereas others, particularly in fundamental biology and translational medicine, continue to rely heavily on *in vivo* models due to the complexity of biological systems (6).

In parallel, strategies to reduce the number of animals per study—such as improved statistical designs, data sharing, and meta-analysis—minimized unnecessary duplication and improved efficiency (7). Additionally, refinement efforts, including enhanced housing conditions, non-invasive imaging, and improved anesthesia protocols, have contributed to better animal welfare and data quality (8). The challenge now lies not only in developing and validating alternatives, but also in ensuring that all 3Rs are systematically integrated into research protocols and that their impact is adequately monitored.

The findings showed that the use of animals in Spain between 2009 and 2023, and in the European Union between 2015 and 2022, exhibited substantial variation across research fields, disease models, and species. However, it is important to note a key distinction in data reporting. In Spain, records from 2009 to 2013 referred to the “number of animals” used, whereas from 2014 onward, they report the “number of animal uses.” In contrast, the European Union consistently reports the “number of animals.” This discrepancy in reporting criteria introduces a challenge when making direct comparisons across time periods and between Spain and the EU.

The analysis of animals used across research fields and disease models during 2009–2013 revealed important patterns in Spanish scientific priorities and experimental practices. Fundamental biology consistently accounted for the highest number of animals used, with peaks in 2009 that later declined. In parallel, research fields focused on medical, dental, and veterinary product development maintained relatively stable use levels, indicating the ongoing necessity of *in vivo* models in pre-clinical safety and efficacy testing and reflecting the persistent demand for *in vivo* models in biomedical studies.

Disease-specific analysis further highlighted the prominence of human biomedical research particularly “other human diseases” and cancer, which together accounted for the majority of animals used in disease-related studies. Interestingly, despite global efforts to reduce animal use, certain research areas maintained a stable reliance on animal models between 2009 and 2013, likely due to the slow development and acceptance of alternative methods in areas such as immunology, oncology, and neuroscience, where *in vitro* or computational models are not yet fully validated. (9).

Between 2014 and 2020, basic research consistently represented the field with the highest number of animal uses in Spain, reflecting its central role in generating fundamental biological knowledge and serving as a cornerstone of biomedical investigation. During this period, the number of animal uses in basic research remained relatively stable, fluctuating slightly but showing a modest downward trend overall. However, a notable shift occurred in 2021, when translational and applied research surpassed basic research in total animal uses for the first time in the recorded period. This trend continued into subsequent years, with 2021 marking a peak in translational and applied research, where nearly 800,000 animal uses were recorded, more than double the number reported in basic research that year.

The variability observed in species-specific usage underscores the evolving landscape of animal research in Spain and Europe. Mice consistently emerged as the dominant model organism across all periods, reflecting their unmatched utility in fields such as genetics, oncology, and neuroscience. Their widespread use is driven not only by scientific suitability but also by regulatory familiarity, which facilitates ethical approval and enhances experimental reproducibility. This trend is consistent with patterns reported by Carbone (2021), who estimated that approximately 111 million mice and rats were used annually in U.S. research, accounting for over 99% of mammals in National Institutes of Health (NIH)-funded laboratories (10) The preference for mice is not merely a European phenomenon but reflects a global reliance on this species, supported by their well-characterized biology, the availability of genetically modified strains, and compatibility with current regulatory and methodological standards (11,12).

Fish, particularly zebrafish and other teleost species, have gained increasing importance as alternative vertebrate models. In Spain, fish were prominently used in fundamental biology in 2009 and 2010, and though their numbers declined in subsequent years, they remained one of the top species employed as alternative vertebrate models, offering both ethical advantages, such as potentially reduced sentience, and practical benefits, including rapid reproduction and optical transparency for *in vivo* imaging (13).

At the European level, zebrafish use peaked in 2016 (513,011 animals), while other fish (including sea bass) showed sharp, episodic increases, such as the spike in “other fish” in 2018 and salmonids in 2021

The COVID-19 pandemic presented unique challenges to research institutions, raising concerns about potential disruptions in animal research due to logistical constraints and shifts in funding priorities. However, the findings indicated that total animal use remained stable when comparing the pre-COVID period (≤ 2019) to the post-COVID period (> 2019), suggesting that research facilities adapted effectively to these challenges. The continuity in animal experimentation may have been facilitated by maintaining breeding colonies, prioritizing essential studies, and redirecting efforts towards pandemic-related research without significantly compromising other ongoing investigations.

Despite these findings, some limitations must be acknowledged. The inconsistency in data reporting practices across different institutions and time periods may have influenced the interpretation of results. Additionally, external factors such as funding fluctuations, policy changes, and technological advancements likely play a significant role in shaping animal research trends but remain difficult to quantify in a retrospective analysis.

Moving forward, standardizing data collection methods and promoting international collaboration in animal research reporting will be essential to improve transparency and comparability of findings. The development and validation of alternative models should be prioritized, ensuring that emerging technologies are both scientifically robust and widely accepted by regulatory agencies. Future research should focus on identifying the key drivers of change in animal research, assessing the effectiveness of the 3Rs, and refining strategies to balance scientific progress with ethical responsibility.

By addressing these challenges, the scientific community can work towards a more cohesive and ethically responsible approach to animal research, ensuring that future studies are conducted with maximum efficiency, transparency, and scientific rigor.

5. Conclusions

The use of experimental animals in Spain and the EU remained relatively stable over the past decade, despite external challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Basic research dominated animal use initially, but translational and applied research gained prominence in recent years.

Mice consistently remained the most used species, reflecting their centrality in biomedical research across regions.

There is growing reliance on fish models, indicating a shift toward alternative vertebrates with lower ethical impact.

Use of higher mammals such as dogs and primates stayed low, underlining the impact of ethical regulations and societal concerns.

Overall, the results reinforce the need for continued monitoring, standardized reporting, and active implementation of the 3Rs principles to improve transparency and reduce animal use in scientific research.

Supplementary Materials: Table S1: Descriptive statistics of animals used across research fields in Spain (2009–2013); Table S2: Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in the number of animals used across research fields in Spain (2009–2013); Table S3: Descriptive statistics of animals used across disease models in Spain (2009–2013); Table S4: Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in disease models in Spain (2009–2013); Table S5: Descriptive statistics of animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023); Table S6: Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in the animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023); Table S7: Descriptive statistics of animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023); Table S8: Significant post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in animal use across years in disease models in Spain (2014–2023); Table S9: Significant post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in animal use across disease model categories in Spain (2014–2023); Table S10: Descriptive statistics of animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19; Table S11: Wilcoxon test with Bonferroni correction assessing differences in animal species used in Spain before and

after COVID-19; Table S12: Wilcoxon test with Benjamini-Hochberg correction assessing differences in animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19; Table S13: Descriptive statistics of animal used in the European Union before and after COVID-19; Table S14: Wilcoxon test with Bonferroni correction assessing differences in animal species used in the European Union: Pre- and Post-COVID-19; Table S15: Wilcoxon test with Benjamini-Hochberg correction assessing differences in animal species used in the European Union: Pre- and Post-COVID-19; Figure S1: Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animals across research fields in Spain (2009–2013); Figure S2: Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animals across disease models in Spain (2009–2013); Figure S3: Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023); Figure S4: Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023); Figure S5: Normality assessment: histograms and q-q plots of animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19; Figure S6: Normality assessment: histograms and q-q plots of animal usage in the European Union before and after COVID-19.

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